

The occurrence of bunt of rice in Bangladesh

I. Hossain, M.Z. Rahman, and G.A. Fakir, Department of Plant Pathology, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh 2202, Bangladesh
E-mail: ismail@royalten.net

Bunt of rice is caused by *Tilletia barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. and Syd. The status of bunt at three selected sites in the northern part of Bangladesh—Bogra, Rajshahi, and Rangpur—was studied over 2 y (1999 and 2000). At each site, four *upazillas* (administration units), with one village per *upazilla*, were selected. Twenty farmers were randomly selected from each village. Just after harvest, farmers' seeds of all varieties were collected and brought to the laboratory. Thousands of seeds per sample (80 samples location⁻¹ each year) were tested. Rice seeds of 1999 boro and 2000 aman were investigated. The varieties/cultivars of rice were BR1, BR2, BR9, BR10, BR11, BR14, BR16, BR20, BR22, BR26, BR28, BR29, BR30, IR50, China, Iraatom-24, Pajam, Pariza-76, BRP, Pancahabati, Type, Tipea, Khatobada, Sarna, Gocha, Aman, P. Kaila, and 532. Collected seeds were tested according to detection methods described by Agarwal and Srivastava (1985). Moreover, collected seeds were categorized into different grades 0 to 5, where 0 = no infection, 1 = up to 10% area of the seed infected, 2 = 11–25% area, 3 = 26–50% area, 4 = 51–75% area, and 5 = >75% area. The study followed a completely randomized design.

The significantly highest samples (33.8%) were found to be infected by bunt in Rajshahi in 1999 (boro season), with 0.14% infected seeds (Table 1). But, in the

2000 aman season, the highest seed sample infection (27.5%) was recorded in both Bogra and Rangpur, with 0.04% and 0.05% seed infection, respectively (Table 1).

The grading of the seeds' level of infection revealed a wide variation of infection, irrespective of location and category of infection (Table 2). It has been observed that most of the infected seeds were either under grade 1

or grade 5. The findings of this study clearly show the existence of bunt of rice in Bangladesh. These findings are important to researchers as well as rice growers in the country as a basis for further study.

Reference

Agarwal VK, Srivastava AK. 1985. NaOH seed soak method for routine examinations of rice seed lots for rice bunt. *Seed Res.* 13:159-161.

Table 1. Incidence of bunt of rice in Bangladesh, 1999 and 2000.^a

Site	Rice variety (no.)	% sample infected		% seed infected	
		1999	2000	1999	2000
Bogra	15	2.000 b	27.500	0.010	0.040
Rajshahi	19	33.750 a	13.550	0.140	0.030
Rangpur	13	2.500 b	27.500	0.004	0.050

^a1,000 seeds sample⁻¹ (80 samples location⁻¹ in each year) were tested. Data in the column with a common letter do not differ significantly at P≥0.05.

Table 2. Grades of infection of seeds.

Cropping year	Site	Infection grade ^a					
		0	1	2	3	4	5
1999	Bogra	99.990	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.003	0.006
	Rajshahi	99.860	0.030	0.010	0.003	0.018	0.080
	Rangpur	99.996	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.004
2000	Bogra	99.960	0.010	0.004	0.003	0.001	0.020
	Rajshahi	99.970	0.002	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.020
	Rangpur	99.950	0.010	0.005	0.000	0.005	0.030

^aInfection grade: 0 = no infection, 1 = up to 10% area of the seed infected, 2 = 11–25% area of the seed infected, 3 = 26–50% area of the seed infected, 4 = 51–75% area of the seed infected, 5 = >75% area of the seed infected. For each sample, 1,000 seeds were inspected.

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